

Extraction Studies of Palladium(II) with 4-S-Benzyl-1-*p*-Cl-Phenyl-5-Phenyl-2, 4-Isodithiobiuret (BPPTB)

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The extraction studies of Pd(II) with 4-S-benzyl-1-*p*-Cl-phenyl-5-phenyl-2, 4-isodithiobiuret have been studied in detail and the analytical procedure for the determination of Pd in micro amounts has been suggested. The stepwise conditional stability constants of 1:2 complex were determined by Yatsimirskii's and Leden's methods and are found to be $\log K_1 = 5.45$, $\log K_2 = 5.39$ and $\log K_1 = 5.56$, $\log K_2 = 5.18$ respectively.

THE survey of the chemical literature shows that, in general, thio-organic compounds are very reactive with the platinum metals. Several sulphur containing reagents are reported to be good extractant for palladium¹⁻⁸. Though 4-S-benzyl-1-*p*-Cl-phenyl-5-phenyl-2, 4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) was firstly reported⁹ in 1903, no attempt was made to study its complexation with palladium. Indeed this reagent with its anionic-SH group and the basic >NH group having structure :

seems to be ideal for the formation of extractable chelates.

It is the purpose of this communication to establish the scope of application of 4-S-benzyl-1-*p*-Cl-phenyl-5-phenyl-2, 4-isodithiobiuret, to solvent extraction of the palladium. The work described below has shown its potential utility for the said purpose. This paper deals with the various aspects of Pd(II)-BPPTB extraction studies in water-iso-amyl alcohol system.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions : Standard palladium perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving chloride free palladium hydroxide obtained from the log of palladium chloride (Johnson-Matthey) in perchloric acid and was standardized gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime¹⁰.

The reagent was synthesized according to the method of Mahajan and Paranjpe¹¹ and was purified by

repeated crystallization from ethanol to get the melting point 127°. (Found : C, 61.47% ; H, 4.31% ; N-10.95% ; Cl, 8.05% ; S, 14.82%. Calc. for C₂₁H₁₈N₂ClS₂ ; C, 61.17% ; H, 4.37% ; N, 10.20% ; Cl, 8.59% ; S, 15.33%). Fresh solution in distilled iso-amyl alcohol was used.

Perchloric acid stock solutions of interfering ions containing 0.01-0.1 mg of test ion per ml, were used. All other chemicals used were of A.R. (BDH) quality.

Apparatus : Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Beckman model DU2 spectrophotometer and 1-cm quartz cell. The pH adjustments were made with a ELICO pH meter model LI-10.

General procedure : An aliquot of palladium perchlorate solution containing less than 75 µg of Pd in 10 ml, at pH 0.5-1.0 was extracted with 10 ml of reagent solution for 10 min and the absorbance of the organic phase was measured at 350 nm against the similarly processed reagent as a blank. The amount of Pd extracted was computed from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra of BPPTB : The reagent exhibits two peaks, one at 225 nm ($\epsilon = 2.02 \times 10^4$) and second at 305 nm ($\epsilon = 1.96 \times 10^4$) in iso-amyl alcohol. It gives only one peak at 258 nm ($\epsilon = 2.80 \times 10^4$) in the aqueous solution of pH 12.0. It follows the Beer's law in the concentration range of $1 \times 10^{-5} - 6 \times 10^{-5} M$ at 258 nm. Further it was observed that 1.0 M of NaClO₄ does not interfere in BPPTB determination.

Distribution of reagent : A 10 ml solution of BPPTB of known concentration [BPPTB]_{tot} in the iso-amyl alcohol was mixed with equal volume of aqueous layer at pH 0.3-12.0. After equilibration, the concentration of BPPTB in the aqueous phase [BPPTB] was determined at pH 12.0 by noting the absorbance at 258 nm where it follows the Beer's law

and reading from the calibration curve. The distribution ratio, D_R of the reagent was determined as :

$$D_R = \frac{[\text{BPPTB}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{BPPTB}]}{[\text{BPPTB}]}$$

The results for *iso*-amyl alcohol are reported in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Distribution of reagent as a function of pH.

It can be seen from the Fig. 1 that the distribution of the reagent is independent of hydrogen ion concentration in the pH range of 2.0–9.0. However, below pH 2 and above pH 9 low distribution was found, which might be due to the protonation and the dissociation of the reagent respectively.

Proton–ligand stability constants of BPPTB : If K_1^H and K_2^H are proton ligand and protonation constants of the reagent and P_R be the partition constant, then the distribution of the reagent, D_R may be given as^{1,2} :

$$\frac{1}{D_R} = \frac{K_2^H \cdot [H^+]}{P_R} + \frac{1}{P_R} + \frac{1}{P_R K_1^H \cdot [H^+]} \quad (1)$$

At low pH, equation (2) is valid.

$$\frac{1}{D_R} = \frac{K_2^H \cdot [H^+]}{P_R} + \frac{1}{P_R} \quad (2)$$

Thus, the plot of $1/D_R$ against $[H^+]$ at lower pH (0.3–1.5) gives a straight line with intercept $1/P_R$ and the slope K_2^H/P_R .

The negative slope region of Fig. 1 holds

$$\log \frac{P_R - D_R}{D_R} = pH - \log K_1^H \quad (3)$$

The plot of $\log (P_R - D_R)/D_R$ versus pH at higher pH gives the value of $\log K_1^H$.

The BPPTB distribution data analysis, yields the values of $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ and $\log P_R$ as 10.14, 0.60 and 1.11 respectively. The value of $\log K_1^H$ from the potentiometric method^{1,3} has been found to be 10.68 at 0.4 M ionic strength (NaClO_4) in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium, which is in good agreement with the above value.

Spectral studies of Pd-BPPTB complex : Spectral studies of Pd-complex reveals only one peak at 355 nm ($\epsilon = 2.55 \times 10^4$). The system obeys Beer's law within the concentration range of 0.3 to 10.0 $\mu\text{g Pd ml}^{-1}$ of *iso* amyl alcohol. The effective working range was found to be 1.0–7.5 $\mu\text{g Pd ml}^{-1}$ of *iso*-amyl alcohol by Ringbom curve. The Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 355 nm is 0.0042 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$. The complex is stable for 12 hr.

Effect of acid and reagent concentration : The extent of Pd (30 μg) extraction remains same at the fixed reagent concentration (1.4×10^{-4} M) within the range of hydrogen ion concentration 0.10–4.0 M (HClO_4). However, at very high concentration of BPPTB (0.01M) the lower range of hydrogen ion concentration for quantitative extraction changes from 0.10 M to 0.003 M (Fig. 2).

Effect of metal ion concentration : The effect of metal ion concentration has been investigated on the Pd extraction at different pH and the study ruled out the possibility of polymerization in the working range of metal concentration (1×10^{-5} – 7×10^{-5} M).

Effect of ionic strength : The distribution of palladium was studied at various concentration of sodium perchlorate (0.4–4.0 M) at pH 0.5, and it was observed that the extent of extraction remains same upto 1.0 M of NaClO_4 . However, extraction decreases at above 1.0 M of NaClO_4 .

Effect of solvents : Amongst the several solvents tried (benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, carbon disulphide *iso*-butanol), and *iso*-amyl alcohol *iso*-amyl alcohol was preferred because of high sensitivity of reagent in it and its high extractability towards Pd chelate.

Time of equilibration ; Pd-BPPTB system was equilibrated for times varying from 0.5–30 min. The extraction was quantitative at about 2 min and hence a time of 10 min was arbitrarily chosen for the entire extraction studies.

Effect of diverse ions: Various ions which are usually associated with Pd in alloys, etc, were tested for interference. The tolerance limit was set at the amount needed to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of Pd and are incorporated in Table 1. It is seen from Table 1 that silver and gold interfere seriously. The small amounts of platinum, rhodium, and ruthenium do not interfere, while other ions can be tolerated in moderate amounts. Almost all the tested anions do not interfere seriously at the experimental condition. The molybdate and tungstate get precipitated at pH 0.5. After removal of the precipitate, the Pd can be easily extracted.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS (Pd=30.86 μ g, pH=0.5, BPPTB=4.35 $\times 10^{-4}$ M)

Ion	Added as*	Tolerance limit (μ g)
Ag ⁺	AgNO ₃	None
Au ³⁺	HAuCl ₄	None
Co ²⁺	CoSO ₄	11,600
Cu ²⁺	CuSO ₄	5,200
Fe ²⁺	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ ·FeSO ₄	23,000
Fe ³⁺	NH ₄ ·Fe(SO ₄) ₂	17,000
Hg ²⁺	HgCl ₂	2,000
Ni ²⁺	NiSO ₄	8,000
Pt ⁴⁺	H ₂ PtCl ₆	90
Rh ³⁺	RhCl ₃	30
Ru ³⁺	RuCl ₃	50
F ⁻	NaF	22,000
Cl ⁻	KCl	27,000
Br ⁻	KBr	40,000
SO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ SO ₄	49,000
SO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ SO ₃	20,000
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	1,000
S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	1,000
Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ⁴⁻	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄	None
WO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ WO ₄	None
PO ₄ ³⁻	NH ₄ H ₂ PO ₄	1,000
SCN ⁻	NH ₄ SCN	600
BO ₃ ³⁻	H ₃ BO ₃	6,000
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	9,000
CH ₃ COO ⁻	CH ₃ COOH	8,000
COOH ⁻	HCOOH	2,400
Citr ³⁻	C ₆ H ₅ O ₇	9,500
Tart ²⁻	C ₄ H ₄ O ₆	14,800
EDTA ⁴⁻	EDTA (disodium salt)	9,800

* The water of hydration, omitted due to the brevity.

Precision: The precision of the method was estimated by applying the recommended procedure on a series of fifteen solutions, each containing 15.43 μ g Pd. A mean absorbance of 0.360 ± 0.005 at 355 nm was found. Average and maximum relative deviations were found to be 0.43% and 0.61% respectively.

The method is rapid, simple and selective and permits separation and determination of Pd at tracer levels. Entire determination takes only 30 min.

Composition of the extractable species: The 1 : 2 (Pd : BPPTB) composition of the extractable species was determined by Job's¹⁴ method as applied by Kabadi et al.¹⁵, mole ratio¹⁶ and slope ratio¹⁷ methods, which was supported by the plot of log D_{Pd} (distribution ratio of Pd) versus log [BPPTB]_{org} (concentration of BPPTB in the organic phase at equilibrium).

Fig. 2. Extraction of Pd (30 μ g) as a function of acid (HClO₄) concentration at
 Δ — Δ BPPTB concentration of 1.4×10^{-4} M
 $\bullet$ — $\bullet$ BPPTB concentration of 4.35×10^{-4} M
 $\circ$ — $\circ$ BPPTB concentration of 1.00×10^{-2} M

Metal-ligand stability constants: The overall stability constant obtained by Job's method¹⁴⁻¹⁵ and Harvey and Manning's equations¹⁶ were found to be 3.532×10^{10} and 1.148×10^{11} respectively.

The conditional metal-ligand stepwise stability constants of Pd-BPPTB chelate were computed from the spectrophotometric data by Yatsimirskii's^{18, 19} and Leden's²⁰ methods.

Yatsimirskii's method: The calculations by this method were made with the help of following equations²¹:

$$\lim_{[R] \rightarrow 0} f_i = \lim_{[R] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\epsilon}{[R]} = a_i = \epsilon_i \cdot B_i - \epsilon_1 \cdot B_1$$

$$[R] \rightarrow 0 \quad [R] \rightarrow 0$$

$$\lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} \epsilon = b_1; \quad \lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} g = \frac{\epsilon - b_1}{Y} = b_2$$

$$Y \rightarrow 0 \quad Y \rightarrow 0$$

where, f, g=Subsidiary functions

a, b=Intercept values

$$Y = \frac{1}{[R]}$$

ϵ =Extinction values.

To determine the conditional metal-ligand step-wise stability constants by Yatsimiskii's method the calculated values of f_1 have been plotted against free-ligand concentration at equilibrium $[R]$ and extrapolated to zero value of $[R]$, (Fig. 3) which give a value

Fig. 3. ○—○ Function f_1 as a function of the free-reagent concentration.
●—● Function f_2 as a function of the free-reagent concentration.

of 6.2×10^9 for a_1 . A curved function was obtained near the stoichiometric point of titration where dissociation of the complex occurs. The extrapolation was necessary since the experimental points obtained from the absorbance values corresponding to the free-ligand concentration in the range $1.0 - 2.2 \times 10^{-6}$ moles/litre indicated some deviation from the usual plot. Inherent experimental error led to deviations in the said range, as the absorbance values were sufficiently low in the region. Moreover, a change in f_1 value from 6.1×10^9 to $6.2 \pm 0.5 \times 10^9$ did not affect the result appreciably and $\log K_1$ or $\log K_2$ values remained

Fig. 4. ○—○ Molar extinction coefficient ϵ as a function of the reciprocal of free reagent concentration.
●—● Function "g" as a function of the reciprocal of the free-reagent concentration.

within ± 0.1 . The function f_2 plotted against $[R]$ (Fig. 3) illustrates the linearity of the function and the intercept gave $a_2 = 4.9 \times 10^4$. The plot of ϵ versus Y yielded the intercept $b_1 = 2.62 \times 10^4$ which is the theoretical molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) for the Pd chelate. The corresponding (ϵ) value calculated from Beer's law was found to be $(2.55 \pm 0.05) \times 10^4$. This suggests clearly that the extrapolation was in the right direction. The plot (Fig. 4) of the function 'g' against Y gave $b_2 = -1.75 \times 10^{-2}$. Thus the value for K_1 was found to be 2.833×10^5 and K_2 turned out to be 2.466×10^5 (Table 2). The molar absorptivities ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 for the species MR_1 and MR_2 are 2.19×10^4 and 2.62×10^4 respectively.

Leden's method: Formation constants values by this method were obtained from considerations of the following:

$$\lim_{[R] \rightarrow 0} \Psi_1 = \lim_{[R] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Psi - 1}{[R]} = K_1 = \beta_1$$

$$[R] \rightarrow 0 \quad [R] \rightarrow 0$$

$$\lim_{[R] \rightarrow 0} \Psi_2 = \lim_{[R] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Psi_1 - K_1}{[R]} = K_1 \cdot K_2 = \beta_2$$

$$[R] \rightarrow 0 \quad [R] \rightarrow 0$$

Where, Ψ = Degree of complex formation

Ψ_1, Ψ_2 = Subsidiary functions.

The stability constant K_1 by Leden's method was found by graphical extrapolation of the function Ψ_1 as the intercept on the ordinate, the value obtained is 3.6×10^5 . The values of β_2 from Ψ_2 function is 5.45×10^{10} ; which gives the value of $K_2 = 1.514 \times 10^5$ (Table 2).

It seems from the Table 2 that the overall, conditional metal-ligand stability constants as well as stepwise stability constants obtained by these different methods agree well with each other.

Absolute stability constant: If β_{ab_s} is the equilibrium constant for the reaction:

then²²

$$\beta_2 = \beta_{ab_s} / \alpha_{H^2} \tag{4}$$

where,

$$\alpha_H = 1 + K_1^H [H^+] + K_1^H \cdot K_2^H \cdot [H^+]^2 \tag{5}$$

The value of β_{ab_s} is also reported in the Table 2, which was obtained from α_H (9.922×10^9) at pH 0.5 from equation (5).

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS AND THE STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR THE Pd(II)-BPPTB SYSTEM, AT 30±1°C

Yatsimirskii's method		Leden's Method		Job's method	Harvey and Manning's equations
Primary parameters	Stability constants	Primary parameters	Stability constants	Stability constants	Stability constants
$a_1 \times 10^{-9}$ = 6.20	$\log K_1 = 5.45$	$\Psi_1 \times 10^{-5}$ [R]→0 = 3.60	$\log K_1 = 5.56$	—	—
$a_2 \times 10^{-14}$ = -4.90	$\log K_2 = 5.39$	$\Psi_2 \times 10^{-10}$ [R]→0 = 5.45	$\log K_2 = 5.18$	—	—
$b_1 \times 10^{-4}$ = 2.62	$\log \beta_2 = 10.84$	—	$\log \beta_2 = 10.74$	$\log \beta_2 = 10.55$	$\log \beta_2 = 11.06$
$b_2 \times 10^3$ = -1.75	$\log \beta_{abs} = 30.83$	—	$\log \beta_{abs} = 30.73$	$\log \beta_{abs} = 30.54$	$\log \beta_{abs} = 31.05$

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